

History of Technological Development in Animation till Early Computer Graphics

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ABSTRACT:

The aim of this research paper is to construct the exact timeline of the development in technology used for animation, beginning at the paleolithic age, and ending with the rise of digital animation. The research paper consists of a number of investigation and research papers on the various sub topics, as well as a look into official documentations published by companies this paper investigates. This paper investigates animation in 3 major sections; Beginning with the early historical trajectory of animation, the pre-film era and finally the industrialization of animation. The study synthesizes the historical progressions.

Keywords: Animation, Technology, History of animation, Early animated films, Industrialization of animation, Digital animation.

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INTRODUCTION

Animation is an incredible special medium, merging the line of major creative fields of illustration, narrative storytelling and cinematography, a trait which simultaneously makes it especially difficult in the technical aspect. The animation we see today covers behind its stages ranging from concept planning, character and environmental design, scripting, storyboarding, modeling, texturing, rendering, composition, visual effects, editing, which is just to name a few. It's no secret, therefore, that animation had to go through an excessive period of technological development in order to facilitate the tools which permits it to function the way it does now. Studying the evolution of the medium can provide a comprehensive understanding of exactly how the seemingly magical process developed to where it is today, as well as provide an appreciation for the pioneers and inventors which made it all possible. The study of technological development in animation is therefore not solely a study of the mechanism, but of human intelligence, and the extent to which it reaches in the pursuit of a creative outlook on life. This research paper aims to teach or advance one's knowledge of how the tools of one of the most popular entertainment mediums developed, and project the most important faces behind it, to hopefully uncover new insights that contribute to a greater general understanding of the world.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The contents of this research finding, is based upon information collected from a veracity of published articles/research documents, selected from the reliable, often-cited sources. The range of these references range from Published pieces covering the long progressive history of animation, as well as those concentrated on specific subtopics such as the various technologies this paper goes over. "The Hand Drawn Animation Process; Traditional and Contemporary Methods" [10]. Published by Venla Linna, an animator and a specific effects artist, covers the history of animation ranging from cave animation to first Walt Disney productions over 69 pages. The research served to provide the

structural qualities and a proper timeline to the information presented here, as well as key historical points to turn attention towards. A similar purpose served “Digital Advances in Animation, From Traditional To Digital Animation” by [3], who provides more recent research and retells this history and in more detail in a more prolonged format, heavily pointing its attention to modern technology as well.

More focused research was used to discuss the different developments of technology, taking focus on primary sources to ensure accuracy. “Animation in Paleolithic art: a pre-echo of cinema” by [2] are the archeologists who discover the information provided. “The Lumiere Cinematograph” [12] is a 1936 paper, written by Louis Lumiere himself, discussing his own invention. “The Early History of Animation: Saturday Morning TV Discovers 1915” by [14] a member of the Department of Radio-Television-Film Temple University, closely holds the title of a primary source: being written in 1977, by a professional in the field.

This paper analyzes the topic in the historical context focusing on comparing specifically the technology of animation graphics.

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted through the collection of information of both literary works, and scientific articles, followed by an analysis of information and finally its synthesis. Through the course of the research, a collection of over 30 articles and research documents were used based on their contents and relevance to the topic, out of more than 50 viewed. Examples of literary sources used

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The first step of understanding the full historical timeline of animation and its various techniques is understanding how far back we must look, and in order to do that we must identify what exactly animation is. In today’s sense it can be described as a series of images which in close and rapid chronological projection create an illusion of movement in a single image. Though its true definition is simply the art of creating movement from still images, with the name originating from the latin word “animātiōn”, (stem of “animātiō”) which translates to “liveliness” [5]. In this straightforward sense attempts at animation have been observed to emerge simultaneously from different parts of the world [5], with its oldest predecessors dating back to ancient Paleolithic cave art.

Although the clear intention of these pieces to convey either narrative or movement can never be concretely true, the finding made by paleontologist Marc Azema in southwestern france, village of Montignac “Lascaux caves” creates a strong case [2]. This network of over 600 parietal wall paintings depicts 56 images of animals superimposed to create the illusion of movement, most often forward pace of the animals, characterized by multiplications in the legs or tail. Similar effect is achieved through juxtaposition of similar subjects, most notable one found in “Grotte de La Vache” cave displaying several representations of a feline creature in respective stages of running, densely arranged in a linear fashion [2]. Illusion of movement in the form of mental development here is created by hovering a light source over the respective drawings, or simply envisioning it in one's head.

More technical approaches to “animating” have been noted to the Magdalenain culture,[6] (17,000 to 12,000 years ago) found in “Isturitz” cave by Marc Azema and Emmanuel Passemer [2], the subject in question - a thaumatrope, in the forms of a small bone disk 15.7 x 9.5 cm representing a carved out image on either side of the same subject, in different stages of movement; a deer upright on one side, and with its legs tucked in on the other.

“One has to pivot the object rapidly (at 180 degrees, making rapid back and forth movements with the hand holding the object at the base) in order to mentally superimpose the two spatially juxtaposed representations” [2].

Akin to its successors the technique is a pioneer of retinal persistence in creation of illusion of movement. The retina of the eye is what allows our brain to retain the memory of images as they flash rapidly before our eyes [4], the quality over which advantage is taken by modern filmmaking today, and as evident, prehistoric cave civilizations some 17000 years prior.

The turning point for animation technology came in the mid-1700s in the form of the “magic lantern” or the “Stereopticon”, a construction which pioneered the optical projection quality for animation [8]. Invented by the Dutch scientist Christiaan Huygens in 1659 the machine was a hollow box, with the mechanism inside involved several transparent images be placed in front of a light source (a flame which developed into electricity) and expanded up to 50 fold in size through a series of concave lenses placed in front, allowing the image to be projected onto wall or a screen [7]. The illusion of movement, primitively, was created through rapid replacements of these images by hand, and advanced in accordance with technology of the time to mechanical rotations which lined up a limited amount of images and allowed them to be rotated through a lever, slightly increasing the integrations between each “shot”.

The apparatus was first assembled by scientists out of pursuit of studying the optical theory and properties of light [8]. The device was close in its mechanism to camera obscura and earlier invention which allowed a small lens to capture light from an exterior and project it in the form of an image onto a dark interior surface, usually used for studying the sun or eclipses [8]. The magic lantern used the same idea, except in the place of an exterior projection, the image was a fabricated illustration of a photograph with a light source behind it. The exploitation of the magic lantern for scientific study was not long lived, and quickly transitioned to either entertainment or information spreading, due to the quality which allowed the images to be viewed by many people at a time. In many cases the information split between educational or instructional in a variety of moral and ethical fields, cloning the object not only as the originator of today’s cinema, but also widespread propaganda [9].

After projection was acquired, the next step in technological development came in the form of motion fluency in animation. The Phenakistoscope holds an important place in the history of animation, marking the transition between superimposed methods of fluent projection of movement with the Thaumatrope to juxtaposition. In many ways juxtaposition is the superior method, allowing more diverse stages of movement, a linear progression between each one and transitions between various shadows and values. The device itself is a simple paper or cardboard disc divided equally into about 8 - 12 sections with an illustration on each section displaying the progression of movement in a single subject. The mechanism which influences the eyes into perceiving movement involves placing the disc in front of a mirror, and observing the images through the slots, the rest of your vision covering the disc, which upon rotation, creates the illusion of the images moving. The instrument which created movement however lied not in the clever design of the phenakistoscope, but its ability to take advantage of our optical system. Our brain identifies movement if at least 10 images per second are shown to it in coherent progression, and most importantly, one at a time without letting the eye follow the previous or subsequent ones. What allowed the eyes to witness images through phenakistoscope in this manner are the animation slots that blocked these unnecessary transitions from view, permitting only the sufficient scope of view.

When discussing the history of animation it is important to award the close role cinematography played in its development. Just like in animation, its impossible to pin a single inventor of this medium without discrediting or oversimplifying a history of vast and simultaneous advancements in technology, yet for the purpose of providing a general understanding of this expansion in visual storytelling, the focus will lie on a select group of inventors who pioneered some important turning points in history.

Although it’s Thomas Edison who holds the title of the american father of cinema, the invention of motion pictures deserves to be credited towards his team of scientific researchers, at the head of which was William Kennedy Laurie Dickson [11]. Motion picture according to Merriam Webster is defined as;

“a series of pictures projected on a screen in rapid succession with objects shown in successive positions slightly changed so as to produce the optical effect of a continuous picture in which the objects move.”

What gave the Kinetoscope, the title of a motion picture, is several factors invented by Dickenson, first of which being the discovery of light played in projecting images off a celluloid covered film frame. A lightsource located directly behind a film frame projected the visual information through the transparent frame. By perforating the edges of each film (puncturing holes around the perimeter) and attaching individual frames, after which placing them in a box like structure and rotating images

one by one in front of a light source, the result is a small projection of a picture, viewed through a lens situated at the top of the box construction. Kinetoscope was the photographic adaptation (and advancement) of the Magic Lantern and the blueprint for projection cinematography, which came into play around 1897 in the form of the Vitascope. Although kinetograph remains the pioneering technology and the architect for cinematography as we know it today, its popularity during its time cannot be compared to the one it presents as an item of historical significance. The market for such an abstract form of entertainment was not large, and as Frank C Gammon, Edison's marketing agent wrote in 1895:

"The demand for Kinetoscopes (during 1895) has not been enough to even pay expenses of our company In fact our candid opinion is that the Kinetoscope business - at least as far as the regular company is concerned - will be a 'dead duck' after this season."

The Vitascope was then the redeeming augmentation to the kinetoscope. It was invented by Thomas Armat and Francis Jenkins In January of 1896, who later sold the license to market the product to Edison's company [1]. It's mechanism was very reminiscent of that of the kinetoscope, but with the ability to project the image on a large wall or a screen by having frames roll over a powerful light source, which displayed the visual information through a series of size enhancing lenses. The product quickly gathered its popularity nationwide, with its work being displayed in theaters and attracting hundreds of audiences daily, making the biggest problem for Edison's team the ability to supply enough entertainment material.

Figure 1. An Eight-Legged Bison Drawn in Chauvet Cave Proves that Split-Action Movement was Used from the Aurignacian

Drawing: C. Fritz & G. Tossello

Source: [2]

Lumier Brothers; Auguste Marie Louis Nicolas Lumière (1862 - 1954) and Louis Jean Lumière (1864 – 1948) are also incredibly prominent faces in cinematic history for having been inspired by the kinetoscope, released a product which encapsulated the functionalities of a camera and a projector, all while remaining relatively lighter and transportable, largely due to it being operated through a continuous spin of a lever and not electricity. The product was the cinematograph, and its invention would be the turning point in filmmaking, as it marked the beginning of motion pictures. The mechanism inside the compact box was reminiscent of that of a sewing machine. A fork-like lever would attach to the holes in perforated film strips, and transport it in a downward linear motion, with each film passing through a source of light (fig. 1). To control the exposure of the transitions between frames, (which would be tempered with 5 optical persistence) a circular shutter would rotate blocking portions of light from passing through the projection lens (Fig.2).

Figure 2. The Laugerie-Basse Reconstructed Disc in Movement: Experiment of a 'Palaeolithic Thaumatrope' by Florent Rivere

Note: Extracted images from a film documentary directed by Marc Azéma in 2009 (©Passé Simple)

Source: [2]

Theater Optique reminiscent in its function to the Magic Wheel, enlarging a series of images illuminated by a background source of light onto a large screen. Its methods of including a large series of images however required a different rotating mechanism, something which crossed the line between the zoetrope drum and praxinoscopes internal series of mirrors. Figure 3 illustrates the function of this mechanism. A marks the circular construction of mirrors facing the exterior of the circle, C marks the drum rotating the most main and most immediate progressive line of images F the rapid flashes of which create the animation. The row gets collected by drum D and come out from drum E. What allows single images to be projected individually in succession, and subsequently projected onto the screen, is a narrow source of light, located at C, the rays of which upon collecting the color and light information of each rotating image bounce it off a series of mirrors until the images are large enough to fill a large screen in intervals of approximately 100 - 300 milliseconds.

First ever animated project, and one of the first uses of perforated film is widely considered to be the "Pauvre Pierrot" (Poor Pierrot) a 15-minute animated French film created in 1892 by Charles-Émile Reynaud (1844–1918), and projected using the Theater Optique. The animated film features the character Pierrot, and his short journey of meeting a lady. The original film spans about 15 minutes which employed 500 individual hand painted glass frames of moving characters laid over a fixed background. The succeeding title in animation history is appointed to Emile Cohl (1857–1938), a bohemian, caricaturist illustrator, and an inspiration to Walt Disney, and his 2-minute film "Fantasmagorie" (1908), recognised as the first known work of traditional hand drawn animation [15].

Fantasmagorie follows a clown character and his 2-minute journey undertaking various interactions with characters and shenanigans. Notably, the film is much more simplistic in its nature, which accounts for the 700 frames it applied to compose just the 2-minute run time, and the apparently stylistic choice it took to create a shoot in negative film, subjecting the background to black and the illustration in white. Additionally, the original approach Cohl included repeatedly photographing individual frames and placing them over a self-constructed lightbox that creates transparency between each film, and tracing over the image with slight changes to create movement, all while making an effort to maintain a coherent pace without the previewing ability.

Figure 3. Illustration by Louis Poyet in the Instruction Manual, Showing the Interior of Cinématographe in Open Position (Public Domain)

Figure 4. Drawing by Poyet of the Lumiere Cinematographe Camera Mechanism, ca. 1895, Jonathan Silent Film Collection

However, the biggest differentiating factor between it, and the works of its predecessor Reynaud, is the application, or at least a more consistent and excessive incorporation of the most traditional elemental components of animation, including timing, space, squash and stretch, curves, gestures, and poses. When taking in account this criteria, Pauvre pierrot can be most correlated to puppetry than animation, although this does not discredit the role it played in the inauguration of cinematic filming and projecting procedures into animation.

France throughout the 19th century was widely considered the pioneering country of cinema, with the first cinematic devices being assembled and used in primarily that country, yet inventions entering the early 19th century preceded their influence throughout the globe. First feature animated film with sound is Historically considered to be "El Apostol" by Quirino Cristiani (1896 - 1984), and Italian born animator, who early on his life migrated to Argentina, and applied his illustration skills to create a satirical film with its plot centered around the mockery of Argentina's new president; Hipólito Yrigoyen, and his radical attempts of installing liberal agendas in the country.

The Theater optique was the device used to create both the Pauvre Perriott and the El Apostol. It is considered the predecessor to the Lumier Borther's Cinematographe, and Edison's Victograph, with a major differentiating point of each frame having been drawn by hand, whereas in the former they were captured through photographic film. This distinguishing feature allows it to be considered an animation, and sets this medium far from cinema as back in its early stages, and now. Cinema tackles computer graphics, and digital photo editing, and shares almost no creative illustration qualities that defy animation. This differentiation however, is what creates separation in subjects depicted in the two mediums today, Illustration provides the quality of being wide in its range of creative possibilities, but incredibly more time consuming in comparison to cinema's photographic automatism, and it's the combination of these which lead animation to focus primarily on children's entertainment. The characters and settings must be simple in their visual depiction in order for animators to create 15 frames of them per second, but then that does not limit its scope of abstract qualities.

When discussing animation as an industry rather than a medium, it's crucial to mention that the names listed previously in this text apply to pioneers in the medium, yet the first name in the industrialization and assembly line animation practice goes to John Bray, as well as the title behind the first animated series [16]. By inventing a method of stimulating the development of animated film, John Bray creates a system by which animation could become a cinematic medium, and not just the project of individual indie artists. This effort is partially credited towards cel system animation, partially towards systematic division of labor. The "cel system" gets its name from the medium onto which individual frames of an illustration are painted; the transparent sheets of cellulose nitrate or acetate ("cels") [17]. This specific material provides transparent properties to the frames when placed over a source of light - similar to the lightbox of Emile Cohl - crucial for the tracing step. To accommodate the proficient technology, a certain amount of labor and a systematic division of it is required. The prolonged creation period of animation existed prior to its industrialization for the primary virtue of the many frames it required to bring into work optical resistance, and compare its smoothness to photographic cinematography, resulting in an average of 15 - 20 frames a second. Additionally, the process was usually burdened upon a single illustrator, who spent the vast majority of the time retracing designs rather than creating new ones. John Bray, the first person to create an animation production company, was able to do so by separating labor and appointing it based on levels of artistic talent and efficiency. On the spot there would always be multiple persons responsible for the designing, tracing and photographing portion of creation, most of them operating simultaneously and employing the full capabilities of their artistic skills.

Figure 5. 1888 Patent Illustration (Top View):
A=praxinoscope, B=axis, C=crown with protruding pins,
D=reel drum with film, E=reel drum, F=flexible band, attached to drum E

Walt Disney is perhaps the most recognizable name and his work the most widespread production when it comes to the sphere of animation. It is no revelation to say that Disney was able to bring the animation industry onto a new level of mass production, leveling it on the same field as cinema up to this day, and the outcome of that sits on the bases of developed workforce. Walt Disney himself excelled not as an illustrator, but a manager able to appoint illustrators in the right direction and provide them with techniques to clean up and speed up their work. By not only dividing labor based on designing and tracing, but into delegations for story, color, inking, scene design, stylising, creating layout, special effects and filming. Storyboarding, a crucial step in animation today, is coined by Walt Disney's production team. His excessive steps in the direction of achieving organized continuation of work centered around first character and setting design, storyboarding, several stages of rough

animation development ranging in number of frames per second which would be created by one team before being passed onto the following one appointed for the smoothing out the chopped movement and filling out the gaps of missing frames between each one. Though it wasn't solely meticulous structural assignments of roles that allowed Disney's production to surpass the bar, teams of animators were trained to replicate reality to the extent caricature illustration permitted,

“Walt Disney organized visiting ‘experts’ to come guide young animators through life- drawing classes and give them nightly ‘action analysis classes’ where they would be walked through live action film clips, pointing out observations that could be made of the movement.” [10]

Additionally, the physical and anatomical accuracies in Disney animation resulted from “rotoscoping” a technique traditional animators use to this day where they trace over real footage of actors moving in accordance to how the character needs to move in the animation.

Figure 6. A Performance of Pauvre Pierrot as Imagined by Louis Poyet, Published in La Nature in July 1892

The pursuit of realism was largely present in the formulation of backdrops as well as the characters, meaning the necessity of the impression of depth as well as light and shadow which create the atmospheric effect of emergence. The invention of a MultiPlane camera is what ultimately permitted Disney and the majority of animation in the following 2 decades to bring their production to the next level [18]. A camera would be pointed towards multiple panes of glass onto which overlapping backdrop details would be added creating a mechanism in the style of a closing curtain on theater stages (figure 7). Similar vertical designs would be used, emulating miniature movie sets (figure 8). The benefit of this technology was not only in executing depth qualities of realism, but saving money on production. This phenomenon is best captured in Disney's production in the 30's and 40's, which conveniently for the large part center around fairy tales set majorly in forests and natural environments, the monotonous scenery of which allows easy plausibility of repeating trees, plants and other indistinguishable backdrop details. This did not only save managers money on timely repeatedly illustrating and relocating insignificant details, but avoided any copyright issues which could arise if the projects were set in urban areas.

Figure 7. Emile Cohl using the lightbox

Source: the bioscope.net

Figure 8. Emile Cohl; shots from Fantasmagorie

Source: Animation mentor.com

The beginning of digital animation of the transition of physical to computer graphics happened in correlation to the development of technology. The first ever form of digital computer was invented in the 1930's in the wake of the cold war, and for the following 2 decades used primarily for military purposes, employing it as a tracking device for aircrafts during the Cold War. The first application of this product in the form of digital imaging emerged in the 1960's in the USA's defense department as a means of gaining technology in preparation for the cold war nuclear arms race, and NASA's scientific development. However, it wasn't long until computers became a widespread commodity, and opened the gate for the first computer graphics to emerge. The extent of visual possibilities of animation only went as far as the technology permitted, and the first computer graphic animation was created By John Whitney on an analog computer modified from M - 5 aircraft system of the 1950's or the *oscilloscope* for the opening sequence of Alfred Hitchcock's "Vertigo", which showcased 4 minutes of a series of abstract coloured shapes in moving across the screen

Figure 9. The Multiplane Camera in the Creation of Snow White (1937)

Source: Patentyogi

Figure 10. Another (Vertical) Version of the Multiplane Camera

Source: Patentyogi

Finally, the history concludes at CGI (computer generated images), which only saw a development in their complexity since their release of *Vertigo* in 1960. A notable turning point for character animation in particular happened in the 190's with the adaptation of biochemical lab computers that analyze human motion into character cgi. The invention of the technology is credited towards Tom Clavert, a professor of kinesiology and computer science at Simon Fraser University who attached potentiometers (devices used to detect electric potential) onto patients to detect physical abnormalities. This device would then be adapted as a motion capture apparatus, that would use

the analog of a potentiometer to capture motion information and convert it to digital form. This would first appear mainstream through the film *Terminator* (1984), as partial integration of CGI onto live action.

CONCLUSION

Overall, the aim of this research paper was to highlight the rich history and technological advancements that have shaped animation into the dynamic and diverse medium it is today.

To summarize the findings of this research paper, it begins at the prehistoric age of cave art and concludes with CGI in the 20th century. Beginning with the rudimentary forms of animation observed in ancient Paleolithic cave art, the paper explored early animation technologies such as the Thaumatrope and the Magic Lantern, then delving into the pre-film era, highlighting pivotal innovations like the Phenakistoscope and the emergence of cinematic animation with inventions like Thomas Edison's Kinetograph and the Lumière brothers' Cinematographe.

This paper also heavily examines the industrialization of animation and its pioneers like John Bray and Walt Disney, who brought to life the cel animation system and systematic division of labor that laid the groundwork for large-scale animation production. Furthermore, the paper covers some history regarding the transition to digital animation, from the first computer-generated images in the 1960s to the adaptation of motion capture technology in character animation.

From ancient cave paintings to CGI blockbusters, this historic timeline not only serves to inform how animation technology has emerged and been integrated, but emphasize humanities pursuit for greater means of creative expression as exemplified by the rapid means with which they achieved it. The trends observed through this history could also be used as basis to predict the path into which society will develop its form of entertainment, seeing how it has been driven by continuous innovations and expansions, the future will likely present enhanced realism, and more immersive experiences. As animation continues to evolve, it is likely to remain a dynamic and influential medium for storytelling, entertainment, and artistic expression, as it has been for thousands of years.

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